

Medium Effect on Tetrahydroxy-1,4-Benzoquinone

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The electronic absorption spectra of tetrahydroxy-*p*-benzoquinone (THBQ) are studied in organic solvents of different polarities, in mixed organic solvents and in aqueous solutions of varying *pH*'s. The different types of interaction liable to occur in solution are discussed. The ability of the compound to form molecular complexes in ethanol media is investigated. The spectral changes with *pH* indicates that the four OH-groups are ionised simultaneously and only an overall *pK* value is obtained. The possibility of multistep ionisation is investigated by studying the titration behaviour of the compound at different ethanol concentrations.

THE absorption spectra of *p*-benzoquinone derivatives have been the subject of many investigations¹⁻⁶. The bands observed were shown to be due to $\pi-\pi^*$ and $n-\pi^*$ transitions; these studies did not include tetrahydroxy-*p*-benzoquinone. Tetrahydroxy-*p*-benzoquinone was used as an internal indicator for the determination of sulphate⁶.

It is aimed in this paper to study the electronic absorption spectra of this compound (THBQ) in organic solvents of varying polarities and the ability of the compound to form molecular complexes with these solvents. The stability constants of the molecular complexes are determined from the spectra in mixed organic solvents. The spectra in aqueous buffer solutions as well as the titration behaviour are studied to throw more light on the mode of ionisation of the OH groups of the compound.

Experimental

Tetrahydroxy-*p*-benzoquinone (A. R. grade) was obtained from commercial source (E. Merck). The solvents used for spectral measurement were purified according to the recommended procedure¹⁰. $10^{-2}M$ stock solution was prepared by dissolving the accurately weighed amount of the material (THBQ) in the appropriate volume of the required solvent. Solutions of lower concentrations were obtained by accurate dilution. The *pH* was adjusted by the modified universal series of Britton¹¹, which also served as supporting electrolyte. *pH* measurements were carried out using a digital *pH*-meter model PHM 64 Research *pH*-meter accurate to ± 0.001 *pH* unit. The absorption spectra were recorded on a Unicam SP 8000 ultraviolet recording spectrophotometer within the wavelength range 200-700 nm, using matched 1 cm silica cells. All measurements were carried out at 25°.

Results and Discussion

I. Spectra in Organic Solvents :

The spectra of THBQ (Table 1, Fig. 1) indicate that both λ_{\max} and ϵ_{\max} of the absorption bands are readily influenced by the nature of the solvent used. The spectra comprise mainly two absorption bands, the first of which at ~ 312 nm is attributed to $\pi-\pi^*$ transition within the quinone nucleus. The other band observed in the visible region within the wavelength range 430-530 nm is a broad one and can be assigned as $n-\pi^*$ transition⁴. This band however, suffers blue shift in ethanol ($D=26$) relative to ether ($D=4.335$) and dioxane ($D=2.2$) which supports the $n-\pi^*$ assignment of this band. The observed blue shift of the $n-\pi^*$ band on increasing the polarity of the medium can be explained on the basis of the nature of intermolecular H-bonding established between solute and solvent molecules. In alcohol, the lone pair of electrons of the hydroxyl group of the compound act as an electron donor to the ethanol molecule (bonding I) which uses the energy of the n -electrons leading to the observed blue shift relative to ether and dioxane in which the oxygen atom of the solvent acts as electron donor to the hydrogen of the OH-group of the compound (bonding II) and hence easier excitation of the n -electrons.

It is observed also that the $n-\pi^*$ band exhibits splitting to two bands at 440 and 480 nm in ethanol. This splitting may arise from the fact that the band contains two $n-\pi^*$ transitions since the compound

Fig. 1

 TABLE 1— λ_{\max} AND ϵ_{\max} FOR THBQ IN ORGANIC SOLVENTS

Solvent	$\pi-\pi^*$ ethylenic		$n-\pi^*$	
	λ_{\max} (nm)	ϵ_{\max} ($\text{cm}^2 \text{mole}^{-1}$)	λ_{\max}	ϵ_{\max}
Ethanol	312	10,000	482	47
Ether	312	43,750	518	74
Dioxane	312	24,000	515	59

has two carbonyl groups^{1,2}. The splitting is not apparent in ether or dioxane, which indicates that the two $n-\pi^*$ transitions have slight different energies. This difference becomes somewhat appreciable in ethanol due to the higher energy of the n -orbitals as explained above.

II. Spectra in Mixed Organic Solvents :

The effect of increasing ethanol concentrations on the spectra of $3 \times 10^{-3} M$ THBQ dissolved in ether or chloroform is investigated (Fig. 1). The study is performed in order to verify the nature of the $n-\pi^*$ band as well as to trace the possibility of formation of molecular complexes via solute-solvent interaction.

The increased proportion of ethanol causes an apparent blue shift of the $n-\pi^*$ band, indicating that the $n-\pi^*$ transition becomes more difficult on increasing the proportion of ethanol. This may be due to the change in solvation energies of the ground and excited states. The difference between the energy of the ground and excited states in ether-ethanol and chloroform-ethanol is higher than in the case of pure ethanol or chloroform leading to the observed blue shift.

To verify whether the shift is due to pure dielectric effect or to the change in the strength of the H-bond, the relation given by Gati and Szalay^{1,8} is applied :

$$\Delta \bar{\nu} = a \left(\frac{n^2 - 1}{2n^2 + 1} \right) - b \left(\frac{n^2 - 1}{2n^2 + 1} \right) + b \left(\frac{D - 1}{D + 1} \right)$$

in which n is the refractive index and D is the dielectric constant of the medium ; a and b are constants. The plot of $\Delta \bar{\nu}$ vs $\frac{D-1}{D+1}$ is of non-linear relation in the two systems investigated indicating that the observed shifts are due to factors other than the

dielectric constant of the medium. The shift would be rather ascribed to the change in the strength of the H-bonding between solute and solvent molecules¹⁴.

If the reaction is represented by

then

$$K_s = \frac{[Q \cdots A_n]}{[Q][A]^n}$$

from which

$$n \log A = pK_s + \log \frac{[Q \cdots A_n]}{[Q]}$$

Since the fraction of A involved in complex formation is quite small compared to the quantity added, one can take the analytical concentration to represent the equilibrium one. By substituting for

concentrations of the TBHQ species by the corresponding optical densities, the following relation is obtained :

$$n \log C_A = pK_s + \log \left(\frac{\epsilon_a}{\epsilon_0 A_n} \right) + \log \frac{D_a \cdot A_n}{D}$$

Thus, pK_s can be determined by plotting $\log \left(\frac{D_a \cdot A_n}{D} \right)$ vs $\log C_A$. The values of n determined from such plots amount to 4 which reveal that 1·4 complexes are formed.

The values of pK_s determined for ether-ethanol and chloroform-ethanol are 0.977 and 0.75 respectively, which indicate that the 'molecular complexes are very labile. The stability of these compounds is found to depend on the nature of the low polarity solvent used.

On plotting the excitation energy vs the mole fraction of ethanol (polar solvent) in the two

Fig. 2

systems investigated, broken lines with three segments are obtained. The orientation energy of the solvent molecules around the solute molecule as well as that of the H-bond calculated from such graph are given in Table 2.

TABLE 2—EXCITATION ENERGIES OF THBQ-ETHANOL, IN ETHER AND CHLOROFORM MEDIA

System investigated	E°	E_{\max}	$E_{\text{Orientation}}$	$E_{\text{H-bond}}$
THBQ-Ethanol				
(a) ether medium	53.9	59.4	1.6	3.9
(b) chloroform medium	54.3	59.4	1.8	3.3

(a) E° , E_{\max} = excitation energy in pure low polarity solvent and ethanol respectively.
 (b) E is expressed in K cal/mole.

III. Spectra in Aqueous Medium :

The spectral behaviour of $2 \times 10^{-5} M$ THBQ in universal buffer solution (Fig. 2) show the two bands discussed before. The 312 nm band becomes ill-defined at $pH > 7$ indicating that this band is due to absorption by the non-ionised species.

The visible band (430-530 nm) is a broad one at lower pH 's. On raising the pH value, the broadness of the band decreases and slight splitting is observed; this splitting becomes apparent on increasing the pH value. The band becomes well-defined and nearly suffers no shift with increasing the pH which supports the $n-\pi^*$ assignment of this band.

The variation of absorbance with pH at the specific wavelengths can be utilized for the determination of the acid-dissociation constant of the compound according to the following methods

- (i) The half-height method¹⁵.
- (ii) The limiting absorbance method¹⁵.
- (iii) The modified Colleter method¹⁶.

From all these methods, only one value of pK_a of the compound amounting to 6.7 is evaluated. This unique value is an overall pK for the four OH groups of the compound.

IV. Acid-Base Behaviour :

To clarify the acid-base properties of THBQ, the titration behaviour of $8 \times 10^{-4} M$ THBQ in different percentages of ethanol (Fig. 3), is performed. From this study, the following are achieved.

1. At lower ethanol concentrations up to 16.5% (wt/wt), the titration curve exhibits only one inflection corresponding to the simultaneous ionisation of the four OH groups of the compound.

2. On increasing ethanol content ($> 16.5\%$), the titration curves exhibit two inflections corresponding to two neutralisation steps.

3. The two inflections become well-separated on increasing the ethanol concentration.

4. The colour change from faint violet to pure yellow accompanies the first inflection indicating the responsibility of the first neutralisation step for the colour change.

However, the ionisation of the OH groups of the compound could be represented schematically as follows :

It is clear from this representation as well as the titration curves, that the neutralisation of the four OH groups of the compound takes place in two steps. The two steps are separated due to the intramolecular H-bonding within the THBQ molecule. The presence of this intramolecular H-bond is also revealed from the ir spectra where a band at 2600 cm^{-1} is observed beside another one at 3500 cm^{-1} representing the stretching vibration of H-bonded OH group and OH group not involved in H-bonding respectively. It should also be noticed that the intramolecular H-bonding becomes more stable in the presence of higher concentrations of ethanol leading to the well-separation of the two neutralisation steps.

The pK values of the two neutralisation steps are calculated from the titration curves using the following two methods :

- (i) Half-neutralisation method :

According to this method, the pH value corresponding to the volume consumed at the middle of neutralisation step gives the value of pK .

- (ii) During the titration, part of the acid is neutralised and the pH of the solution is related to the pK value of the acid by Henderson-Haselbach equation :

$$pH = pK_a - \log \frac{[\text{Acid}]}{[\text{Salt}]}$$

The plot of $\log [\text{Acid}]/[\text{salt}]$ against pH gives straight line whose intercept with the pH axis at $\log [\text{Acid}]/[\text{Salt}] = 0$ amounts to the value of pK .

The results of these two methods are given in Table 3.

Fig. 3

TABLE 3— pK VALUES FOR THBQ OBTAINED FROM pH TITRATION CURVES

% of ethanol (wt/wt)	pK_1		pK_2		mean value	
	1st method	2nd method	1st method	2nd method	pK_1	pK_2
34.50	6.2	5.60	9.30	8.5	5.90	8.90
49.47	7.0	7.05	10.10	10.2	7.00	10.15
68.98	6.1	6.60	9.20	9.2	6.35	9.20

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HAMMAM & IBRAHIM : MEDIUM EFFECT ON TETRAHYDROXY-1,4-BENZOQUINONE

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